

Vietnam awards IRRI with Friendship Order

The President of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam awarded the Friendship Order of the Vietnamese Government to IRRI in acknowledgment of the Institute's "very efficient contribution" to food production in Vietnam. The award was received by IRRI Director General Klaus Lampe during the Vietnam-IRRI Rice Conference on 4-7 May.

Rice is cultivated on 5.9 million ha, or 80% of the arable land, in Vietnam. Once a major rice-exporting country, Vietnam was a net importer for more than two decades. It became a net rice exporter again in 1988, and now exports approximately 1.5 million t of rice annually.

Planting modern early-maturing rice varieties, improving management resources, and implementing appropriate government policies have been responsible for Vietnam's recent production increases. Since 1968, 42 breeding lines

have been released in Vietnam. IRRI varieties now cover 60% of the irrigated rice-growing area in the Mekong Delta.

Vietnamese scientists are working closely with IRRI. Some 319 Vietnamese researchers, scholars, and fellows—many now holding key positions in rice research institutes—have received training at IRRI. Researchers at the Cuc Long Delta Rice Research Institute and IRRI have been collaborating to develop hybrid rice technology for farmers in the Mekong Delta provinces since 1983. ■

Rice training network proposed by Asian countries

Twelve Asian rice-growing countries have proposed the establishment of an Asian Rice-based Training Network to share expertise and training materials, strengthen relevant training programs, and accelerate research being done to boost rice production.

The proposal came from a conference convened by the Thailand Rice Research Institute, Kasetsart University, and IRRI to share rice-related training activities and experiences among participants and to better understand training constraints of national programs.

Conference participants were heads or directors of rice-related training institutes and programs in Bangladesh, Cambodia, China, India, Indonesia, Myanmar, Lao PDR, Nepal, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Vietnam as well as IRRI staff. Also represented were the Asian Vegetable Research and Development Center, the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics, the International Irrigation Management Institute, and the United Nations Development Programme.

Based at IRRI, the proposed network would communicate and document information relevant to rice-related training. It would explore and develop new training strategies and coordinate in-country training programs. Membership would be open to rice research organizations or universities. ■

First-time release of hybrid rice in India

India recently released its first-ever hybrid rices for commercial cultivation, the first in the world for tropical rice cultivation.

India is the fourth country to release commercial hybrid rice, following China (subtropical and temperate rice hybrids), Vietnam (subtropical), and the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (temperate).

Two of the Indian hybrids—APRH-1 (IR58025A/Vajram) and APRH-2 (IR62829A/MTU9992)—were released by the Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University in Hyderabad. The Tamil Nadu

Agricultural University in Coimbatore released the third hybrid—CORH-1 (IR62829A/IR10198-66-3R). Four more hybrids will be released shortly.

"The concerted efforts of Indian rice scientists, with technical support from IRRI, have made it possible to release the first set of hybrids in India after only four years of work," says Dr. S. S. Virmani, IRRI plant breeder and hybrid rice expert.

More than 400 experimental hybrids, either developed in India or introduced from IRRI, have been evaluated in India. About 30 hybrids demonstrated a yield advantage of one ton or more per hectare over the local varieties. ■

Rice germplasm exchange program proposed for the Mediterranean and West and Central Asia

Researchers in the Mediterranean and West and Central Asia may soon be swapping improved rice germplasm with the rest of the world through the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER). The proposed exchange program will help researchers in these regions broaden the rice genetic base and identify superior varieties.

"The recent relaxing of political barriers and the improved communication among countries in these regions provide an excellent opportunity to promote unrestricted exchange and evaluation of rice germplasm," says Dr. F. A. Bernardo, IRRI deputy director general for international services.

The germplasm exchange and evaluation program will involve countries that grow Basmati and fine-grained aromatic rice. They include Afghanistan, India, Iran, Iraq, and Pakistan in West Asia and the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan in Central Asia.

The proposed germplasm exchange program also hopes to link the Mediterranean with other countries growing japonica rice, such as Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, China, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Republic of Korea, and Japan.

"The project, if funded by a donor, will greatly improve and stabilize rice yields in these regions," says Dr. Bernardo. "Promising varieties and breeding lines will be evaluated to find new superior varieties for release and to identify valuable breeding lines to improve local varieties. The project will also develop scientists' skills through degree and nondegree training." ■